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An interferon switch in preeclampsia.

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We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in the placenta in normal pregnancies and in cases of severe preeclampsia to discover novel markers of disease in pregnant women with preeclampsia. We report here discovery of an interferon switch during severe preeclampsia. Ifnb1 and Ifng were the third and fourth most differentially expressed genes across the transcriptome when comparing the human placenta in uncomplicated pregnancy and in severe preeclampsia. However, while Ifnb1 was silenced in severe preeclampsia, Ifng was activated. An interferon switch is active and evident in severe preeclampsia in humans.

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